

ARCTIC PASSION

Deliverable 7.1

Policy support for the Arctic Science
Fundors Forum

(previously planned as "Policy support for ASM
and Forum of Arctic Research Fundors")

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ARCTIC
PASSION

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Executive Summary

A better coordinated and integrated, more useful and more equitable pan-Arctic Observing System of Systems (pan-AOSS) is needed to monitor effectively the rapidly advancing environmental and climate-related changes in the Arctic, with sustained funding being essential to its success. With the diverse expertise of the Arctic PASSION consortium, recommendations were formulated summarising concretely what needs to be funded for a long-term pan-AOSS. In Arctic PASSION's Work Package 7, the first step towards this goal was a dialogue with the Arctic Science Funders Forum (ASFF). In a closed workshop with the members of the ASFF, we learned about challenges and possibilities for a sustainable pan-AOSS from a funder's perspective. Main challenges are the complexity of organising international funding programmes, as most funding streams are coordinated nationally and comply with national priorities. Additionally, funded research activities are mostly short-term and project-based. However, on the positive side, some specific research needs can be covered by these short-term funding programmes and if research goals are based on clear societal relevance, it is easier to justify and receive funding. Also, ways to combine open access with data sovereignty were shared showing that this topic is high on the agenda.

The effort towards an improved and sustained pan-AOSS is of ongoing relevance and Arctic PASSION's dialogue with the ASFF was very helpful in that process. There might also be potential in looking into other funding areas, such as environmental agencies that fund time series and monitoring programmes. Generally, the Arctic PASSION recommendations were supported by the funding agencies and there was a willingness to work together internationally, even when the countries could not offer funding support.

1. Introduction

Task 7.1 and Deliverable 7.1 focus on policy support for the Arctic Science Funders Forum. It was originally planned also to target the Arctic Science Ministerial (ASM) (previous title of D7.1: “1. Report presented at Policy support for meeting with ASM and Forum of Arctic Research Funders”). However, since the Russian full-scale invasion of Ukraine has changed the geopolitical situation and Arctic cooperation, the fourth ASM that was supposed to be jointly organised by France and the Russian Federation did not take place. Norway, chairing the Arctic Council since May 2023, decided not to organise an ASM during its Chairship. A second change to the title of the Deliverable, more of an editorial nature, reflects the change of the name of the Funders Forum: formerly called Forum of Arctic Research Funders, now named Arctic Science Funders Forum (ASFF).

The ASFF is an initiative resulting from the second ASM in Berlin, Germany 2018. The Forum includes the funding agencies of the countries participating in the ASMs as well as the Arctic Council Permanent Participants and builds a platform for bilateral and multinational exchange about new and enhanced collaborative scientific activities in the Arctic, priorities, activities and opportunities.

The dialogue with the ASFF is one element of the engagements with policy makers carried out by Work Package 7. It is a key step towards identifying long-term funding opportunities for a pan-Arctic Observing System of Systems (pan-AOSS), and by that a critical part of the legacy of Arctic PASSION.

In this deliverable you will read about the project’s engagement with the ASFF, what is needed in order to fund a long-term pan-AOSS and its challenges and possibilities.

2. Engagement with the Arctic Science Funders Forum

Since the start of the Forum’s work, the German Arctic Office at the Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI AO) has been part of the German delegation, participating in the ASFF meetings. Through this involvement, channels of communication had been established. However, after the start of the Russian invasion of Ukraine, the ASFF like the Arctic Council was set on pause. Only in autumn 2023, did the Forum start its work again with a meeting held in conjunction with the Arctic Circle Assembly 2023 in Reykjavik, Iceland. AWI AO was in close communication with the chair of the Forum also during the pause and

briefly reported on Arctic PASSION at that meeting. A few months later, AWI AO attended the session “Arctic Science Funders Forum – connecting funders and scientists on Arctic research planning and international collaboration” at the Arctic Science Summit Week in Edinburgh, UK on 24 March 2024. The session was organised by the ASFF, and AWI AO supported the organisers in the interactive breakout sessions. On 18 October 2024, at the next annual ASFF meeting, which was again held during the Arctic Circle Assembly, a more detailed overview of Arctic PASSION was presented. As part of this presentation, AWI AO invited the members of the Forum to an Arctic PASSION workshop on the sustainability and long-term perspective of a pan-AOSS to be held in conjunction with the Arctic Frontiers Conference 2025 in Tromsø, Norway. This workshop, entitled “Way forward toward a long-term funded Arctic Observing System”, took place on 29 January 2025 in hybrid format and provided the opportunity for a direct dialogue between ASFF members and Arctic PASSION participants, addressing the possibilities and limitations in funding a sustained pan-AOSS (see chapters below).

At the Arctic Frontiers Conference, AWI AO also contributed to the session “[International Polar Year \(IPY\) V: Research, Data and Science Cooperation](#)”. The presentation focused on perspectives from the Arctic PASSION project on “How to sustain an improved and more useful Arctic Observing System?”. Additionally, AWI AO participated in the side meeting “On the Future of Arctic Science Funding”, which was organised by the Norwegian Research Council, the current chair of the ASFF.

3. Arctic PASSION recommendations for the ASFF

The workshop, held in conjunction with the Arctic Frontiers Conference 2025, was the main mechanism for Work Package 7 to interact with the ASFF. To enable a meaningful dialogue, AWI AO in consultation with the whole Arctic PASSION consortium prepared a set of recommendations regarding the needs for a better coordinated and integrated, more useful and more equitable, long-term sustained pan-AOSS, including the funding requirements.

At the end of 2024 a survey was performed within the consortium. 22 responses were received as free-text responses across all Work Packages of the Arctic PASSION consortium: 61% of responses by male participants, 35% were female participants, 4% contributed as anonymous; of the total, 31% were early career professionals.

These responses are summarised in recommendations towards a better coordinated Arctic Observing System, with improved observations and a structured Arctic Data System covering three categories:

1. Coordination and Governance
2. Observations
3. Data

CATEGORY 1: TOWARDS A BETTER COORDINATED ARCTIC OBSERVING SYSTEM

RECOMMENDATION 1.1.

Need for sustainable coordination of an Arctic Observing System

(including observing networks, Indigenous Peoples, local communities, research institutions, organisations, different levels of governance such as municipal administrations, stakeholders, end-users, managers of systems/equipment/logistics/infrastructures, international field campaigns, ...)

Why? The plethora of actors involved in Arctic observations needs a platform for cooperation and coordination. With a multilateral dialogue among the actors, observations and services can be better targeted towards societal needs and benefits of communities. It improves the exchange of existing observations as well as the Arctic data structure and sharing. Through a coordination platform, end-users and target audiences can be better involved in the co-design and prioritisation of variables, platforms and delivery interfaces.

WE RECOMMEND FUNDERS TO:

Find a mechanism to sustainably fund long-term observations in the Arctic, and their coordination:

- Support SAON (Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks) and its Secretariat in a substantial and long-term capacity to continue their mission to facilitate, coordinate and advocate for coordinated international pan-Arctic observations.
- Long-term commit to the [European Polar Coordination Office](#), a newly established coordinating body connecting European projects, initiatives, the science community and the European Commission. This coordination office on the European level and a North American equivalent will also be an important body in the structuring of a coordinated Arctic Observing System. Similarly, sustained funding for thematically focused coordination efforts is of high relevance, also, such as for the Arctic Ocean Regional Alliance - ArORA.
- Support the inclusion of relevant intercultural, cross-sectoral and transdisciplinary actors in funding calls to contribute to enhancing international institutional cooperation, e.g., between research institutions and municipal administrations and/or communities across the Arctic. Ensure that a breadth of multifaceted perspectives and individuals are included in decision-making towards an Arctic observing network, e.g., in terms of disciplines, knowledge systems, governance levels, communities, sectors, end-users, genders, ages, socio-economic strata, ethnicities, etc.

RECOMMENDATION 1.2.

Support [SAON's ROADS process and the SAV Expert Panels](#) and members, in particular support for Indigenous contributions (co-leads, members, speakers, etc.) is needed

Why? SAON's Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems (ROADS) aims to improve Arctic observing and data systems through better and new partnerships. The Shared Arctic Variables (SAV) concept defines sets of observables that can help to solve problems on a local or regional scale in the Arctic. SAVs are responsive to the information needs of everyone affected by the rapid changes taking place in the Arctic. The idea is to draw on the capacity of all the communities to co-design and co-manage observing efforts by gathering representatives from each into thematic Expert Panels, and to include Indigenous Knowledge and Local Knowledge as well as science into the process. Results from the Expert Panels will contribute to SAON's ROADS process. The two projects, Arctic PASSION (EU & Canada) and [RNA CoObs \(Research Networking Activities for Sustained Coordinated Observations of Arctic Change, USA\)](#), (co-)funded the establishment of SAV Expert Panels to pilot a set of SAV themes. When the projects end, SAON will need support to continue.

WE RECOMMEND FUNDERS TO:

- Invest in SAON's ROADS process and the development of Shared Arctic Variables by supporting SAON financially.

RECOMMENDATION 1.3.

Enhance the sharing of logistical platforms through a network of research stations and research infrastructures

Why? A network of infrastructures is needed to stay connected, share sampling protocols, and harmonise data collection across the Arctic. Arctic PASSION has shown how important and challenging it is to harmonise data collections that date back a long time, to fill gaps, and to make them comparable between stations. Especially stations that are setting up new weather stations and ecological monitoring benefit greatly from being connected with a network of stations that have a long history of monitoring such parameters. Networking activities and sharing best practices will also help identify gaps in monitoring. This network includes Automatic Weather Stations (AWS), a key infrastructure that provides instantaneous measurements and long-term trends.

WE RECOMMEND FUNDERS TO:

- Find mechanisms for long-term funding of the [INTERACT Non-Profit Association](#), a network of 74 research stations and infrastructures (plus an additional 21 Russian stations currently on pause), such as core funding and a host office. The network works on improving data collection and accessibility, knowledge exchange on measured parameters and shared challenges, as well as research access. INTERACT is also represented in SAON (see 1.1.).
- Provide continued funding for maintaining existing infrastructures such as scientific Automatic Weather Stations (currently removed, unmaintained or inoperable after project's end) (low cost-effort).

RECOMMENDATION 1.4.

Equal inclusion of Indigenous Peoples, and other Arctic (or local) communities and their organisations as well as other (marginalised) groups and the equity of different knowledge systems

Why? Indigenous Peoples, and other Arctic (or local) communities are closely connected to the Arctic environment and have unique and valuable knowledge. Together with academic knowledge, changes in the Arctic can be interpreted holistically and the quality and relevance of data can be improved. There are high barriers and bureaucracy to involve them as partners, little time to build collaborations before writing a proposal and therefore difficulties to co-create projects without funding salaries, etc.

WE RECOMMEND FUNDERS TO:

Change the funding and decision-making structure to a more equitable and inclusive Arctic observing system:

- Funding streams for dedicated inclusive and holistic approaches in Arctic research.
- Allow Indigenous Peoples, and other Arctic (or local) communities or their representing organisations to lead their own projects, be beneficiary partners and co-leads in research projects.
- Flexible funding for the pre-proposal phase to establish relationships/partnerships and to involve community members without an administrative overhead (compensation for time).
- Funding to hire trusted local facilitators who can build trust, share knowledge, and encourage the use of the service. Workshops and training sessions are also essential to ensure that communities understand and benefit from the system while contributing their own observations.
- Allocate resources for programmes that enable Indigenous Peoples, and other Arctic (or local) communities to participate actively in data collection, monitoring, and interpretation processes. This may include training, employment opportunities, and long-term partnerships to support local experts and community-based observing networks.

CATEGORY 2: TOWARDS IMPROVED OBSERVING SYSTEMS

RECOMMENDATION 2.1.

Long-term funding for long-term monitoring is key: Long-term observations are the foundation on which detection, understanding and prediction of climate change and its effects are based.

Why? The impact of ongoing climate change and increased human activity in the Arctic can only be understood based on long in-situ time-series. Long-term measurements are important to have a baseline to compare with and to understand rates of change and are also needed in regions, where currently no major environmental or climate-related changes are happening. Many long-term records are obtained by short term projects, leading to inconsistent and intermittent time-series, and missing standardisation. For sustained and more appropriate long-term observations, we must move away from this ad hoc approach.

WE RECOMMEND FUNDERS TO:

- Establish a mechanism to sustainably fund long-term observing and monitoring systems/programmes in the Arctic. Evaluate options for separate funding streams for research projects and for long-term monitoring tasks. Existing infrastructure must be maintained after the implementation phase. Focus should lay on long-term monitoring of essential key variables (e.g., climate variables) and new Shared Arctic Variables.
- Allocate funding (10-year horizon) for equipment/logistics/infrastructure and running costs of in-situ observation systems with a sufficient geographical coverage. Representative in-situ observations are inherently valuable, but are also needed for calibration and validation of remote observation systems and models.
- Put the mechanisms and multinational resources in place to allow researchers, Indigenous Peoples, and other Arctic (or local) communities as well as other actors from different nations to develop bottom-up projects to address key Arctic concerns. Similar to how the EU performs their science, but on a truly international scale. Multinational funding allows for optimal use of expertise and infrastructure as well as facilitation of data/results integration.

RECOMMENDATION 2.2.

Monitoring and observations must be based on societal needs

Why? Understanding the Arctic's complex socio-economic-environmental dynamics requires closing gaps in interdisciplinary research that addresses both environmental and socio-economic data needs. Research that combines environmental science, economics, and social science allows a better assessment of the impacts of environmental change on Arctic communities, economies, and ecosystems, as well as the inclusion of Indigenous Peoples, and other Arctic (or local) communities, users, stakeholders and relevant audiences.

WE RECOMMEND FUNDERS TO:

- Fund interdisciplinary research to address socioeconomic and environmental interdependencies.
- Request funding applicants to create a framework for assessing the socio-economic benefits of data articulating their value and potential impacts to society.
- Collaborate more in the development of research targeting the influence of local climate mitigation and climate adaptation policies on societal behaviour and methodologies for integrating societal behaviour concepts into climate governance at different governance levels. Observing systems and the related interdisciplinary research should lead to a sufficient level of knowledge/understanding to capture local climate change and related environmental issues.

- Require that funding calls ensure that observing systems be rooted in and flow into useful services which provide the current state and future outlook for information relevant to users outside of research: business, public sector and the general public. These services should be able to demonstrate that they reach such audiences.
- Support a pilot phase project to achieve consensus in communities on monitoring approaches and monitoring needs.
- Funding is needed to identify and fill the gaps in monitoring. Networking activities can help identify gaps.
- Include gender- and sex-disaggregated data in Arctic observations by supporting additional research time to gather statistics on the gender of data generators and users as well as information on inequalities or discrimination. Invest in training research teams about this component.

RECOMMENDATION 2.3.

Model-based support for designing an observation network and investment in a better use of new technologies

Why? When setting up new or improving existing observations, modelling can help to calculate and to make scenarios about which methods (frequency, spatial/temporal resolution, etc.) are most effective to cover the object of observation. Also, technologies themselves can be better used to overcome limitations.

WE RECOMMEND FUNDERS TO:

- Include a modelling approach when designing new observation networks or optimising existing ones.
- Be open to different observation modalities to maximise the potential of new technologies, which are usually developed for reasons and areas other than environmental monitoring.

RECOMMENDATION 2.4.

Need to funding research on critical gaps in cryosphere science

Why? Arctic PASSION monitors key cryosphere components such as sea ice, snow, permafrost, lake and river ice, glaciers and ice sheets because they are highly important to societally relevant issues such as food security, infrastructure, safe navigation and transportation, and way of life.

WE RECOMMEND FUNDERS TO:

Fund specific activities to fill cryosphere knowledge gaps:

- Invest in machine learning-related methods to monitor Arctic land ice.
- Invest in new satellite missions, especially satellite altimetry to monitor glacier mass changes.
- Invest in field observations for Arctic freshwater fluxes and subglacial discharge to understand ice-ocean interactions.

CATEGORY 3:

TOWARDS AN IMPROVED ARCTIC DATA STRUCTURE AND BETTER KNOWLEDGE SHARING

RECOMMENDATION 3.1.

Improved data handling and provision

Why? Arctic data and metadata are still often handled and published in a fragmented manner which makes it difficult for various users to access and use the data. Producing standardised and FAIR data and metadata improves the interoperability, accessibility, use and re-use. Together with an open access, it builds the basis for knowledge, education and decision-making. The more comprehensive and detailed metadata available to describe the data record, the easier it is to find and use the actual data.

WE RECOMMEND FUNDERS TO:

- Require data generators to create and treat data and metadata records in accordance with state-of-the-art data management standards throughout the process of data generation to publication. Acknowledge the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles for research data management and ensure practical implementation that makes published data machine-readable. Funded scientific projects and activities should include research data management at the level of an independent work package as the standard procedure.
- Continue to require open access publication of research data in funding calls. Reserve sufficient funding for project partners for publishing articles and data with open access.
- Provide funding for timely production and dissemination of real and near real-time data and value-added products that are useful for services to society.
- Provide funding for local and remote infrastructures and citizen science to support standardised collection and transfer of data and metadata to trusted long-term data repositories, ensuring the use and reuse by the scientific community, local stakeholders, decision-makers and the global public. Specific funding can be allocated in research projects or through a network mentioned under 1.3.
- Ensure the acceptance and establishment of the CARE (Collective benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics) principles when data and observations originate from Indigenous Peoples' communities or activities.

RECOMMENDATION 3.2.

Improved data integration, use and sharing

Why? Long-term data repositories archiving and publishing research data according to the FAIR Data Principles require continuous funding to support their services in curating and publishing submitted data, ensuring interoperability, keeping up with growing standard requirements, and training researchers and institutions, leading to significant benefits for science and society at global, community and individual levels.

Also, on other levels such as the Global Terrestrial Network for Permafrost (GTN-P), it is important to continuously fund experienced personnel and technical infrastructure in order to bring many individual datasets together in a standardised and harmonised format, and to maintain as well as distribute global data products.

WE RECOMMEND FUNDERS TO:

- Provide permanent support for long-term data repositories and data publishers fostering FAIR research data management and facilitating access to machine-readable data at national and international level. Require trusted observation data repositories being harvested by the [SAON Data Portal](#) to aggregate datasets from different data repositories, make the data more

accessible through rich metadata at discovery and use levels combined with data access services following FAIR principles. This allows re-use by, e.g., decision-makers.

- Invest in a more user-friendly interface and structure of the SAON Data Portal to better be able to find existing data for key variables and specific regions/local areas and to be able to pick up on previous measurement campaigns through accessible data and metadata. A dedicated usage case study would help to customise and improve the portal interface for users outside of research.
- Invest in a maintained data infrastructure for [Essential Climate Variables](#) (ECV) monitoring by funding central offices to bring the data and metadata together. For example: funds for the Global Terrestrial Network for Permafrost (GTN-P) office and GTN-P database are needed.
- Invest more in digital transfer and repository solutions for knowledge developed at different levels of governance to enhance multi-level knowledge transfer and further use.

4. Description of the workshop

In preparation for the workshop “Way forward toward a long-term funded Arctic Observing System”, held on 29 January 2025 at the Fram Centre in Tromsø, Norway, the above recommendations were sent to the ASFF. The workshop itself, co-organised by AWI AO and the Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP), was by invitation (ASFF members only) and arranged in hybrid format. Twelve in-person participants and five online participants representing Canada, the EU, Germany, Greenland, Iceland, Japan and Norway as well as Sápmi and the Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks (SAON) attended the meeting. In addition to AWI AO and AMAP, Arctic PASSION was represented by the project coordinator and one additional consortium member. After a welcome and round of introductions, AWI AO presented the Arctic PASSION recommendations and invited each country/region to comment on the recommendations and to talk about their possibilities and limitations of respective funding structures towards a connected pan-AOSS. The workshop concluded with an open discussion also addressing possible next steps.

5. Feedback received by the ASFF

The Arctic PASSION recommendations shared with the ASFF generally found support by the countries attending. Funding agencies commented that some of the recommendations are at least partially or temporarily addressed in research programmes, such as

- the involvement of SAON (**RECOMMENDATION 1.1** subpoint 1) and supporting the development of a Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems (ROADS) (**RECOMMENDATION 1.2**);
- sharing of research infrastructures (**RECOMMENDATION 1.3**);
- supporting coordination efforts (such as the establishment of the European Polar Coordination Office (EPCO)) (**RECOMMENDATION 1.1** subpoint 2);
- involving Indigenous Peoples, and other Arctic (or local) communities in research projects (**RECOMMENDATION 1.4**);
- increasing attention on the societal relevance of projects (**RECOMMENDATION 2.2**).

In the following, we list the feedback and comments during the open discussion at the workshop. The feedback can be grouped into challenges and limitations as well as possibilities towards a long-term funded pan-AOSS.

Challenge & Limitations	Refers to ...
A major challenge in the overall process towards a long-term pan-AOSS is related to its implementation and sustainability, especially maintaining resources and being equitable in how those resources are provided, given the wide variety of requirements for different types of observations.	RECOMMENDATION 2.1 and the effort in general
Creating a coherent, integrated and long-term pan-AOSS is a huge international effort that requires an international programme , which is significantly more challenging in terms of financial commitments.	RECOMMENDATION 2.1 and the effort in general
Some countries pointed out that investments for a long-term funded pan-AOSS are expected to be covered by the research institutions funded by the governments or ministries directly. In this way, the funding for the pan-AOSS would exceed a 10 year-period. The challenge lies in institutional responsibility .	RECOMMENDATION 2.1 and the effort in general
The long-term funding of central coordination offices is difficult: After identifying which structures these are (that step can be short-term project-based funded), it is up to each party to ensure the long-term funding of their own resources. This needs to be done with an equal share of operational responsibilities and financial responsibilities. However, the coordination structures can be funded through projects, but only when they are relevant to the project or when they are newly established.	RECOMMENDATIONS 1.1, 1.3 subpoint 1 and 3.2 subpoint 3
For some funding programmes, the inclusion of end-users in the programme needs to come through the research activities themselves. Other funding programmes, however, directly work on increasing the relevance of research and data collection, by demanding that new projects involve a user group from the very beginning.	RECOMMENDATION 2.2
An aspect that complicates the centralisation of national funds towards a shared international goal is that the relevant countries have different national foci and schedules . One focus mentioned was investments in open science initiatives and having discussions on data sovereignty to avoid data misinterpretation and misuse. This is especially important for knowledge being shared by Indigenous Peoples. Although there is a development to more open access data, results and knowledge, there are limitations. The use of Indigenous Knowledge is governed by ethical standards that must be respected in relation to the dissemination of such knowledge.	RECOMMENDATION 3.1 subpoint 2
The recommendation on equal inclusion of Indigenous Peoples was appreciated. It was raised that there needs to be support for Indigenous Peoples' communities and clear coordination and communication about what kind of research activities are	RECOMMENDATION 1.4

going on. The communities want to be involved and know about what is happening on their lands.	
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Possibilities	Refers to ...
The need to fund research on gaps in cryosphere science can be met in a simple way by funding agencies through short-term research projects. In these short-term projects, the funding can also be used to operate those infrastructures or observing systems needed to carry out the research project.	RECOMMENDATION 2.4
Depending on the country, there might also be funding opportunities outside the short-term project funding streams , e.g., a call for infrastructure of national importance to implement new observatories. A success story from Norway was shared in this context. The funding of the infrastructure call was used to implement the Climate-Ecological Observatory for Arctic Tundra (COAT) and as a successful continuation, the national budget for infrastructure operation took over and has been funding the observatory directly since then. This can also be a solution for sustaining a pan-AOSS.	RECOMMENDATION 2.1 and the effort in general
To gain more interest in research outcomes by politicians and ministries, the degree of societal relevance plays a key role. Making a difference with research projects has become more important. When results are being used by diverse user groups, it is easier for decision-makers to see the added value for the society and, thus, direct funding.	RECOMMENDATION 2.2
To support the development of open access, but still protect the rights of the data owners, especially in terms of Indigenous Knowledge holders, the mobile application SIKU seems to be making good progress. SIKU is a platform for Indigenous Knowledge and observations to connect Arctic Indigenous Peoples' communities supporting land use, language and knowledge transfer, while being mindful of data sharing. Data sovereignty plays a key role on that platform, allowing users to decide for themselves who can access their own data.	RECOMMENDATION 3.1 subpoint 2
Although some countries of the ASFF do not currently have dedicated funding for international efforts or have an unstable budget for Arctic research, a lot of possibilities will also be based on the fact that many countries are very willing to cooperate internationally and to be part of the process. This includes Indigenous Peoples across the Arctic, willing to work together as equal partners, bringing a lot of knowledge on, e.g., interpretation of data and improving data collection.	The effort in general

<p>The challenge lies in creating observing systems that offer everything we desire and maintaining them. However, the key opportunity lies in having more individuals with those skills—not just tied to short-term projects, but also embedded in communities or areas where we might not have fully recognised the value of such expertise. It's in building this capacity and utilising these resources that we can uncover significant potential.</p>	<p>RECOMMENDATION 2.1 and the effort in general</p>
<p>In addition to funding agencies, environmental protection agencies who have funding for national monitoring programmes and fund time series could be an interesting contact to discuss opportunities for long-term monitoring/observations. These agencies are often contracted by research institutes.</p>	<p>ADDITIONAL POINT MENTIONED DURING OPEN DISCUSSION</p>

The discussion during the workshop was limited to the 1.5 hours of workshop. In the end, there was general consensus that the discussion on this topic needs to be continued.

6. Conclusion and next steps beyond Arctic PASSION

The dialogue with the Arctic Science Funders Forum (ASFF) was highly valuable in gaining insights into funders' perspectives on sustaining a pan-AOSS. The ASFF was an important addressee in this phase of the project's process.

The primary challenge for securing long-term funding for a pan-AOSS lies in the fact that most funding efforts are managed on a national level (with the exception of the EU funding programmes) and are focused on nationally prioritised research initiatives. In many countries, new research projects and initiatives are typically supported only through short-term, project-based funding. Only those observation systems directly relevant to the project's objectives are funded for the duration of the grant. Managing and coordinating a long-term perspective remains challenging, especially when it requires an international programme. The combined international efforts and commitment needed for sustained funding for a better coordinated and integrated, more useful and more equitable pan-AOSS remains a significant challenge. Furthermore, if research institutions wish to support the pan-AOSS, the question arises as to how this can realistically be achieved, especially if their budgets from the governments or ministries remain unchanged.

To explore alternative funding options, it may be useful to consider approaching environmental protection agencies, private funders, or foundations, or integrating the pan-AOSS as an additional component of the WMO or Copernicus structures.

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Additional opportunities exist in certain countries or funding programmes that are already addressing some of the recommendations, and many countries, despite lacking funding for an international pan-AOSS, are very willing to cooperate internationally and to be part of the process.

AWI AO will maintain contact with the ASFF, as this dialogue remains important for both sides.

Acknowledgements

We would like to express our thanks to the Arctic Science Funders Forum, particularly to the current chair at the Norwegian Research Council, as well as the two co-chairs at Rannís and the Japanese National Institute of Polar Research, for graciously allowing Arctic PASSION to be presented at the meetings of the Forum and for the openness for dialogue and collaboration! Additionally, we extend our sincere thanks to AMAP for their collaboration in co-organising our workshop at the Fram Centre. We deeply appreciate your support and partnership!